

Transcription of Interview 8

November 2020

Mr Interview 8: Well, I really believe, for me, in our country, when we talk of National Health Insurance, we are referring to both, the funding and also the achievement of universal health coverage. So we are talking about both, preparing the health system to offer services, and parallel to that, also the funding mechanism. I'm sure I thought, NHI, it's actually to just refer to the funding mechanism, but I think, in our country, I come to accept that the term refers to both, preparing the health system, private and public, for universal health access, and at the same time, dealing with the issues of funding.

And when we talk about the universal health access, I guess, what is clear, is that in our country, access has tended to favour those with resources, and those with medical aid would be in full-time employment or maybe self-employment, who can afford, and they have basically enjoyed the bulk of the resources. Whilst the overwhelming majority of the population, I think the numbers, usually, is the 80/20/, 20/80 thing, have been serviced with 20% of the resources, so 80% of the population, or thereabout, have basically have to deal with the 20% of the resources. And NHI, in it's fundamental principles, need **aid** to correct the imbalanced access to health, that has actually continued by this 80/20 access.

And also, I think it's clear that, at some stage, even medical aids were trying to begin to charge more, for the people who are more sick, and the issue of social solidarity was getting out of the window. And I think NHI aims to ensure that the issue of social solidarity between the healthy and the sick, those who have and those who have not, is entrenched in our system. I think, was it our president, at one stage, referred to his experience, I think he quoted the Swedish prime minister, who shared a ward with a factory worker, and that showed him, basically, how far the country had progressed, to say that, whether you're the prime minister or you're a factory worker, access to healthcare should almost be the same. I think that's what we are aiming to do.

Shane: And Mr Interview 8, you mentioned that National Health Insurance, usually, is a funding model, but in our case, you said there was a link with service provision; and do you think the inequality, is why we brought a model that does that? Or why do you think it's different in our situation?

Mr Interview 8: Yes, I think the issue is, one, the inequality of resources, **to say** you can't offer world-class, and up to the standard health system, to 80% of the population having access to 20% of the resources. So if you were to ask me, any reform, any improvement in the health system, was a non-starter, if that resource imbalance pursued; hence, I think when people look back, they would say, from the time we got our vote of freedom in 1996, to to-date, the public service has not improved. And I'm saying it would not have improved, immensely, because of the fundamental funding unfairness. So that's the first thing that I'd like to emphasise, to say, through this, then we can immediately say, we'll see an improvement in the public health service, but we'll also see an improvement in the private health sector. Because very few people can say the outcomes of the private health sector has been better than the public sector, you can't say that. Because it is still the public sector which drives your key indicators; I'm talking of immunisation indicators, your HIV, access and treatment for the HIV

population. You'll find that those key programmes that drive our outcomes and impact on life expectancy and reduce mortality rates on infants and under 5s, those programmes are driven by the public health sector. So what I'm trying to say is, there is no indication that, with all these resources, the private sector has contributed to improving our health outcomes.

What is clear, we have produced, I'm sure, lots of millionaires, if not billionaires, from the medical aid insurance, and other people.

[05:30]

Shane: Definitely. Mr Interview 8, and your views on the current proposal for funding, particularly the strategic purchasing, where there's a separation of the funder, from the provider?

Mr Interview 8: I think, for me, that, definitely, would remove any possibilities of, I would say, corruption, that separation where the purchaser is separate from the funder. And for me, what is key, the way I understood, the profits will be dependent on people keeping the population healthy, than be dependent on number of attendances, etc. So the incentive to keep people sick, as a result of any money, will be removed. But rather a new incentive of keeping people healthy, then maximising a profit, is what the NHI will introduce.

Shane: And with regards to the actual purchasing, who do you think should oversee that? The purchasing of services.

Mr Interview 8: I've never applied my mind, specifically, to say what body should be overseeing the purchasing of the services. But for me, maybe we can build on.. for example, there was this structure that was responsible for overseeing medical aids – what is it? - I'm trying to remember what that structure was. The structure, basically, legally, made sure that they could not discriminate, they could not overcharge, and all those things. I'll remember that structure. But we need a similar type of a structure, that will then oversee the whole health service, private and public, that will ensure that people are funding per capita, in terms of the population they serve, and then, that funding is, obviously, if you start with the population that is more sick, more poor, etc., you might start with more funding. But the more they get healthy, you should then be seeing your profit.

I'm trying to remember the structure which national department used to have, but it was an independent structure, sitting outside the national department, overseeing the medical aids. I don't know whether you remember that, or you know of that structure.

Shane: I think, from the Medical Schemes Act, that they had a separate review board; I don't know if it was the medical schemes board, or something, but definitely to govern them, and rein their expenditure and that.. ja.

Mr Interview 8: Ja, I'm referring to something like that. Because in my view, you still need people who would have an insight in what the health services **mean**, population, not just maybe bureaucrats who might not have an insight into that service.

Shane: And you mentioned the per capita payment; do you think that's feasible, and the best option?

Mr Interview 8: Yes, I think that's easy, and I think that's the best option; but obviously, that per capita, needs, also, to be geographically located, in that you should not take people from different areas, and say, this is my group of people. Because if you are to factor in the level of development of infrastructure, etc., it will be important to [...] locate the population served, so that the funding can then take the level of development of that particular area, into account. The level of issues like employment, in that particular area, into account, and factored into the funding model of our health service.

Shane: And what are your views of working together with the private sector? Do you see any challenges, or opportunities?

Mr Interview 8: [...] opportunities; I would say - and I'm saying this, obviously, subject to correction, if I'm making a mistake - in South Africa, the training of nurses, the training of doctors, the training of all health workers, is done by the public sector, through the public purse.

[10:17]

Shane: Yes.

Mr Interview 8: And then, what happens? The private sector gets people to work, whom they have not even contributed to training. So for me, as I said, firstly, the improvement of the public sector depends on the two systems coming together, private and public. Two, it means pooling of our health resources, in terms of human resources, in particular, and all other resources. I still believe that our **quarternary** type of hospitals, Steve Biko type of hospitals, Chris Hani type of hospitals, will rival any private sector health provision. So I don't think the benefit will be in terms of quality, but it will be, definitely, in terms of pooling the resources. And also, maybe, will benefit it, because they've always been **doing this** profit, so you might benefit, for example, in terms of the management of hospitals, of clinics, etc., better management. We will definitely benefit by the two systems working together, and not in competition with each other.

Shane: Mr Interview 8, you do know a lot about the NHI, as opposed to other people that I have interviewed, so how have you experienced engagement with the NHI policy development, from province or national?

Mr Interview 8: Ja. Firstly, I must say, I've [...] it through a series of presentations, either conducted by national or provincial people, where they would present, and say, this is where they are, and this is the areas of input that they required.. they requested from the group, so they would come - I work for the City of Jo'burg - they would come here and present to our group, we would organise other stakeholders for them to present to, as a City, to say, this is where it's going. More than that, the issues of improving the system, whether be it in terms of the development of community health workers, the ideal clinic implementation; basically, community health workers, is to say, don't wait for people to be sick, see them at home, offer services that you can offer at home, and make sure that we link communities to the services. An ideal clinic was beginning to say that, if we were to have a NHI, the essentials in any clinic, that are required for the clinic to function optimally, whether be it your emergency drugs, your emergency trolleys, your [...], your thermometers; so we've been working together, to ensure that clinics, progressively, are moving towards meeting the standards that are expected towards NHI. So

I've had involvement in inputting in terms of the document, the policy directive, but also I'm also involved on day-to-day, in terms of ensuring that we prepare the public sector to be ready for, to offer that service when the time comes.

Shane: And with regards to the government engaging the public, as well as healthcare workers, or district managers, or the sort, do you think there's been adequate engagement? Or opportunity for people to comment and give input?

Mr Interview 8: I'll talk here, for City of Jo'burg; as I said, we have invited government, we have national and province, we've had a series of presentations, we've organised presentations to be done to our stakeholders, inputs have been requested, and so **start** from them, and forwarded to those bodies. And I know there were parliamentary hearings as well. If I remember well, there was a chairperson, who was a previous **MMC** in KZN, who went to all provinces, as well, taking inputs. So I think communities and health workers, have been engaged, and those who were closer to the subject, who understand the subject, have had a chance to input on the policy direction. And I think, obviously, the inputs will remain polarised, in South Africa, depending on where you are at the moment. So I won't be surprised if they've got opposing inputs, sometimes even from some of the health workers.

[15:18]

Shane: Mr Interview 8, what is your perception about the implementation of NHI, as it stands at the current moment?

Mr Interview 8: You see, if you consider the issue of the pillars, I think there's four pillars of preparing for NHI. Your ideal clinic, your community health workers, and then the specialist support, for example, pregnant women, to reduce maternal mortality and things like that; and I think there's another **stream** that is linked to that. If you consider those, as part and parcel of implementation of the NHI, as opposed to preparing for the implementation, I would say, we are doing very well; there's a focus leadership in what we need to be focusing on. But if we are saying, are we anywhere towards putting a fund, that pooled fund that will fund the services, have we made any progress towards that, I would say, very little. But in terms of preparing for the NHI, I would say we have made excellent progress.

Shane: And why would you say that there has been less progress towards preparing the fund?

Mr Interview 8: I would have thought, by now, if we are moving on the fund, we would be talking about, either issues of amendment to the taxes thing, to cater for the fund, the institutional arrangements for the fund, to say, is it a separate department, and beginning to put it into place. I'm not touching those things, and feeling that the structural readiness to implement NHI, in terms of the fund, is actually moving at the same pace. And I think, also, let's not undermine the disruption that has been caused by covid, in redirecting the focus of many countries, and I think that has definitely slowed down the **issues**.

Shane: And moving forward, what do you think would be the key challenges that district health service managers would have to cope with, in terms of contracting and implementing the NHI?

Mr Interview 8: The first thing, is the perception - and perceptions should be considered real - of many people, that the service is not up to standard. I think they need to ensure that that is corrected, and that can be done through improving services, as we are currently doing, including, instead of people waiting there for the whole day, where people can be going to clinics and hospitals, on appointment basis, and going in and out. So you know what happens, is that the people who wake up and then one hundred and fifty of them queue from five in the morning, and obviously, the last one of that hundred and fifty, might arrive at five and leave at two or four. But if proper SMSs or appointments were sent, people know that [they are] expected there at eight, and expected there at ten, that waiting time will definitely improve services. And I think the issues of attitudes, also, which, in my view, they can't be justified, negative attitudes and judgemental attitudes, towards service providers; but we know that those things are made worse by, actually, the feeling of being overwhelmed by health workers; I'm talking nurses and doctors. If you go in the place, it's full, it's dark, in terms of work environment, it takes away, and then it might affect the issue of attitudes.

But also, just, something that we don't have in our system, debriefing; certain categories of nurses and doctors, particularly people who are exposed to casualties, to your trauma, and things like that, if there's regular debriefing, it will help deal with the issues of attitudes, the state of mind of health workers. So the greatest challenge for managers, district managers, to ensure that people vote with their feet, they want to come for their service, will be the issue of improving our service standards, including waiting times, attitudes, infrastructure, availability of medications, availability of tests, and responses to tests; I think all of those will definitely contribute to improve, both the perceptions of the public, and them voting with their feet, to go towards the district health services or services offered by government, or public sector, at the primary level.

[20:43]

Shane: Okay, Mr Interview 8, then that's all the questions that I have. From your side, is there any other view or thought that you would like to express?

Mr Interview 8: Just to say, remember, there'll always be winners and losers, there are currently people who benefit from the current system, and sometimes, when we look at opposition to the system, we also have to look at it with that lens. Is it because there's something fundamentally wrong with the NHI? Or is it because the person or the institution stands to lose, with this particular reform. That, ja, that will be my closing remark.

Shane: That's perfect. Thanks so much for your very valuable insight and your time. Once I've gotten into word format, I'll send that to you, just to revise this, if you would like.

Mr Interview 8: Okay, thank you; much appreciated.

Shane: Thanks so much. Have a good day.

Mr Interview 8: Bye. Alright, okay, bye.

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